

Flightlines for Burwash Creek, Eastern Denali Fault

Flight path (black lines) with the resultant DTM. Red stars indicate takeoff and landing locations for the collection(s). Satellite imagery from Google.

Note: the 2021 flight lines were calculated with a field of view of 60° (resulting in a narrower spacing), whereas the 2022 collections used a 90° field of view.